

ON THE ISSUE OF DEVELOPING KNOWLEDGE OF FUTURE PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS TO HAVE A POSITIVE INFLUENCE ON STUDENTS' MIND

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Abstract

This article presents opinions on improving the pedagogical, psychological and philosophical knowledge of future physical education teachers to have a positive effect on the psyche of students, and forming a new approach to physical education.

Key words: physical culture and sports, physical and mental capabilities, knowledge and skills, pedagogical approach, pedagogical preparation, pedagogical activity, pedagogical professional competence, aggression and violence character, competent approach, innovative approach.

Today, improving the training system of future physical education teachers, thereby developing their professional competence, and forming general cultural knowledge and skills in them is gaining relevance. In addition to physical education, future physical education teachers need to have the skills to influence their psyche, give them the right motivation, and develop the inner motivations that encourage them to be active. The need for formation is increasing. The reason for this is some problems in physical education, incorrect approaches and a stereotyped view based on seeing physical education only as an increase in physical capabilities and its negative consequences. That is, according to today's physical education, the teacher requires the students to perform some physical exercise, movement, encourages them to know a sport well, and in this regard, the students' capabilities, interests and mental problems 'doesn't pay attention. He evaluates students based on their physical fitness, and tracks students with lower abilities. Through this, he forces them to do physical education, to perform certain physical exercises, to learn and practice their favorite sports. This causes students to lose interest in physical education. The effectiveness of physical education decreases.

Therefore, the task of increasing the pedagogical, psychological and philosophical knowledge of physical education teachers to have a positive effect on the psyche of students, and forming a new approach to physical education is becoming urgent. For this purpose, it is necessary to develop the knowledge of future physical education teachers about the formation of the psyche, to understand and understand the mental, spiritual and emotional state of

students, and to improve the educational methodology aimed at the formation of mental stability along with physical training in education. one of the urgent duties. For this, it is appropriate to consider the operation of general pedagogical principles in physical education and their function, to consider its importance. In the process of physical education, general pedagogical principles can be applied, because this process is a special phenomenon of education and upbringing.

Research on the elimination of changes in the psyche of students through physical education, foreign Gregory K. Patton, Wendell R. Gamer, S. D. Brookfield, R. M. Milgram, Drapeau Patti, Albert Bandura, Richard Walters, Louis Cohen researched by scientists such as In the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS), a number of research works have been carried out in this regard and are still being carried out today. In particular, among the researchers A. Akhmatova, A. M. Derkach, A. S. Glinsky, K. M. Lulikova, I. I. Prodanov, T. V. Zobnitsa, A. M. Leontev, G. V. Mironova, on the strengthening of mental education in students based on physical education, to have a positive effect on their psyche issues related to the development of pedagogical approach and innovative methodology are highlighted. Also, in Uzbekistan, future teachers should develop knowledge and skills to positively influence the psyche of students, especially the competence of physical education teachers to integrate physical education with mental and spiritual education. development issues were studied by pedagogic scientists such as N.A. Muslimov, M. Isakov, R. Yusupov, A. T. Nurmanov, S. Turgunov, H. Roziyev, A. Sh. Soliyev, G. Kh. Tillayeva. The success of any educational process depends on how conscious and active the students are. Correct understanding of the tasks of the physical education process, actively performing them with interest accelerates the progress of education, allows to improve the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities and use them creatively in life. These laws are primarily the basis of the principle of awareness and activity.

There are many motivations for exercising. They are incidental or of little importance from the pedagogical point of view. But in the process of education, they begin to justify themselves. The principle of consciousness and activity is expressed by understanding the purpose of physical training and setting the goal of realizing the perspective of physical fitness and achieving it [3:46].

The tasks given in the course of physical education are performed in the form of certain physical exercises. "In addition to giving exercises to be performed, the teacher should explain to the students not only what to do and how to do it, but

also the fact that it is recommended to do this exercise, and that it is necessary to follow this rule. It is self-evident that the level of understanding of goals and tasks depends on the age and level of training of the participants. In the initial stages of physical education, simple concepts are formed, and later, the participants learn the essence of the work more and more deeply. Exercise is voluntary action controlled by the mind. In the formation of movement skills, the performance of movements is raised to the level of automation. It cannot be said that there is no conscious movement, because one consciously learns physical exercises in order to bring the movement to the level of automation. Teachers and trainers monitor, evaluate and correct the mistakes of the participants" [5:8]. Nevertheless, it is important to develop the ability of the participants to evaluate and control their own actions.

According to the analysis, if a student engages in sports based on his interest, personal desire and need to benefit, or if he strives to show his physical ability and will, the results will be progressive and positive. As a result, the qualities of physical culture are manifested in them quickly and at a high level. "Physical education has a great impact on people, strengthens their health, increases their ability to work, and helps them live longer. Sport is an excellent means of maintaining strength, training height at any age. Sport serves as a source of alternation of work and rest. Physical education of students is an important factor determining the effectiveness of physical education" [7:60]. Therefore, based on the interests and desires of students of higher educational institutions, it is appropriate to direct them to sports, to introduce them to physical exercises, and thus to increase their physical qualities.

Future students of physical education need to improve their professional competence based on new approaches, develop their professional worldview and thinking in order to increase their physical and mental capabilities, strengthen their will and direct their enthusiasm.

The physical skills of a physical education teacher should be developed along with professional competence. Pedagogy creates conditions for the professional formation, development and self-realization of a person and helps to achieve the humanistic goals of society.

There are different approaches in pedagogy:

- a) appropriate pedagogical process of education;
- b) the targeted process of increasing the qualified labor force, training, retraining and improving the qualifications of specialists carried out by the state and society;

c) network of educational institutions - from pre-school education to higher and post-university education;

d) possessing pedagogical training and competencies, etc.[4:29-30].

In the training of future physical education teachers, it is necessary to improve their physical fitness, as well as to strengthen their pedagogical training, and to develop innovative teaching skills. In scientific and scientific-methodical works, the term "pedagogical training" is often used as a synonym for the term "teaching" in relation to all levels of education, including higher education. In addition, both terms are often used as a general concept and do not require a specific definition or explanation. The term "teaching", studied by Russian scientists G. Onushkin and E. I. Ogareva, is used in connection with the practical tasks of education, when it is related to a certain type of activity, practical, refers to the development of pedagogical experience with the purpose of later application to the implementation of specific tasks of the cognitive or educational program. This term is used in two senses:

a) learning - formation of readiness to perform the tasks ahead, reflects two types of activity - teaching and studying, special training in the narrow sense;

b) readiness is the presence of competencies, knowledge and skills to perform the given tasks. Therefore, in future physical education teachers, it is necessary to improve the physical fitness of students, to ensure that they regularly engage in sports, and to direct them to the health process, as well as to study the mental state of students, diagnose and on the basis of which it is required to conduct physical education with them [6:18].

Another scientist, V.A. Polyakova, stated that pedagogical education is a set of special knowledge, skills and abilities, qualities, work experience that provide the opportunity to work successfully in a certain profession, as well as the process of imparting relevant knowledge and skills to students. kidlasa, another scientist Y.N. Galaguzova analyzes the preparation of future teachers for pedagogical activity and evaluates it as the process and result of the formation of preparation for pedagogical activity, which is carried out by mastering the appropriate set of special knowledge, skills and qualifications. Also, V. A. Nikitin, taking into account higher education and social issues, learning the skills of education and teaching in the sciences and special specializations, as well as the skills of analysis and research. refers to the pedagogical activity of understanding the teaching and learning process.

Thus, pedagogical professional competence is the result of preparation for pedagogical activity. Therefore, it is necessary to improve the pedagogical

training of future physical education teachers in the process of teaching, training and developing their professional skills on an innovative basis.

An important factor in the development of the developed countries of the world is the existence of special attention to their education system. That is, the strong attention to education and the introduction of more investment in them, the creation of a competitive environment between private and public educational institutions will also have a positive effect. The development of strong athletes in developed countries, especially the USA, European countries, Japan, Korea, China, and Russia, also confirms this opinion. In Uzbekistan, on the basis of the reforms carried out in recent years, as well as by importing this approach of developed countries into the national education system, high results are being achieved, and a special tradition of discovering the physical capabilities of our youth has begun to form [1:8-9].

When working with students, it is very important for teachers to know their individual characteristics well, because in every class there are students who are smart and restless, active and lazy: those who are interested in physical culture and sports and those who are not. The teacher should know well the health and level of physical development of each student. In every class, there are students who clearly stand out from their classmates in terms of physical fitness. Some of them are unable to perform exercises, while others, on the contrary, show high results when performing physical exercises. The teacher should always encourage and give moral support to students who have difficulty in performing physical exercises and movements. It is necessary to give them a complete understanding of the secrets of mastering physical exercises, the basics of physical training, and to give them confidence that in the future they will also become skilled athletes or physically fit.

"Pedagogical methods such as education and training are widely used to implement the process of physical education. Various methods are used in the process of physical education. These methods are based on direct, emotional perception or the use of words or practical action activities. Loading and rest are considered a unique component of physical education methods and are used in the education process. The order of organizing the load and performing it in combination with rest is considered the basis of the structure of physical education methods" [5:30]. The effect of loading depends on its size and intensity.

The volume of the load is understood as the long-term effect of the given physical exercises and the total amount of physical work performed during the

training. The amount of exercise or training, the time spent on it, the weight of the work performed, the size of the distance covered and other indicators are the criteria.

Load intensity is understood as the combination of the impact force and seriousness of physical work during each exercise in a unit of time. The speed of movement is a measure of the intensity of work, the weight of the weight, the amount of work performed with speed and weight in the total volume of the corresponding load, the motor density of the training, etc.

The load is constant in the composition of various methods of physical education, standard-practice in each exposure and variable in the process of exposure. Methodological principles of physical education determine the appropriateness of using the load.

It will be possible to encourage free choice and free will in physical education by improving the methodology of positively influencing the psyche of students. For example, some students choose a sport that does not suit their character, or their parents make the choice for them. And this turns off their interest in this sport or club and the desire to act conscientiously. Because some students are recreational, they cannot participate in aggressive sports, or even if they do, the results are not effective. That is, they made a mistake in choosing a sport suitable for their character. However, aggressiveness is an important factor in some sports, so aggressive children should choose this type of sport.

Also, aggressiveness and violence in students can show positive results in sports. But over time, students often face mental difficulties after not being able to stop their "aggressive actions. Because he could not change his behavior, he would suffer greatly because he would not be able to live a peaceful life like other people" [8:169]. Therefore, in order to increase the physical capabilities of students, it is necessary to pay attention to the fact that they are engaged in physical education and sports, as well as to direct them to professional sports. However, it is necessary not to become the cause of their mental breakdown and damage, and not to create an opportunity for them to admit their lack of will.

The following functions of pedagogical education can be distinguished in the preparation of future physical education teachers, in the development of their professional competence, in the use of new approaches in working with students, and in teaching in general:

1. Reflection function (from the Latin *relatio* - message) is aimed at the development by students of specific situations acquired during the socialization

of culture (at the level of education, profession, civic virtues, etc.) and pedagogical activities.

2. The regulatory function (lat. Regulare - regulation, direction) is aimed at developing certain standards of behavior and social control of the student's behavior and work.

3. The axiological function (Greek axios - valuable) is related to the existence of a basic value system shared by all or most of its members in any social institution. Inconsistency in the system of values shows the critical condition of the institution and makes it extremely difficult to implement its other functions.

4. Integrative function (lat. integer - whole) indicates that not only the successful operation of a particular social institution, but also the interests of the whole society should be prioritized for the goals and results of pedagogical activity.

5. The educational function is to form a system of knowledge among students about the world in which they operate; education and strengthening of fundamental scientific principles on which economy, production, science, culture are based; formation and development of general and specialized knowledge, skills and abilities of the future specialist as a subject of pedagogical activity. The same function is implemented through the participation of teachers and students in the dissemination of scientific knowledge, results of research and scientific and technical activities.

6. The educational function is (students' interaction in educational, knowledge, production, club-profile and other types) not only important knowledge and skills in the pedagogical field, but also life attitudes and principles, cultural, formation of concepts of social moral norms, values, ideals and standards of behavior related to them. The result of socialization of pedagogical education is a stable system of moral-valued and normative behavior of students in relation to the surrounding world, the profession they are mastering, and themselves. This result is clearly reflected in the education and successful training of the future specialist.

7. The development function is a type of "human institute" that not only provides pedagogical knowledge and skills, but also develops personality, prepares it for an independent creative life, real self-realization. At the stages of education, the main criteria of human development are intelligence and creative thinking, self-awareness and development, the concept of self-development is necessary, including the organization of emotional-volitional and motivational-need aspects.

8. Worldview function - formation of a holistic worldview and attitude of students in line with modern achievements. A graduate of a higher education institution should have appropriate social work and creativity skills, build his own life, living environment and interaction.

Today, the idea of a competent approach is actively developing in the field of pedagogy in the world and in our country. The initial conditions for the formation of a competent approach were considered the emerging social order for the training of teachers flexibly connected with the changed realities of the modern world and the functional content of pedagogical activity. In the conditions of growing processes of integration and the interaction of cultures, it is necessary not only to have deep professional knowledge in the chosen field, but also to be flexible to the changing social conditions, that is, not only to be a pedagogue, but also the task is to prepare a future teacher who realizes that he is the owner of his own destiny. Communicative culture and the potential for self-development, the ability to make decisions in non-standard situations - it is important to develop these qualities [2:27].

Development of professional competence of future physical education teachers on the basis of innovative approaches, development of their knowledge and skills in working with students and having a positive effect on their psyche is carried out on the basis of a competent approach. Because the physical and mental qualities of future physical education teachers are formed based on the integration of various competencies.

Physical education teachers must perform the following tasks in order to form physical fitness in students, to strengthen their will by having a positive effect on their psyche: to ensure that the lesson passes at a high level and to complete the physical education program of the corresponding class; together with the doctor, conduct the medical examination of the students on time and take into account the results of the medical examination in their work; to ensure that the places where classes are held are kept in an appropriate sanitary and hygienic condition; to ensure that all students do physical exercises in comfortable clothes; participation in the organization and holding of extracurricular physical education clubs and the wide involvement of students in them; carrying out explanatory work on the importance of physical education of students; regularly improve their knowledge in the field of physical education; it was considered to make the weavers interested in physical culture and regularly engage in physical exercises in them.

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